

A Proposal for Recognizing Skills in Data Science Using Open Badges

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Abstract

The growing demand for data scientists and their importance in industrial trends has resulted in a number of recent initiatives to promote skills in data science. One of these initiatives is a badge based scheme for the recognition of skills in data science developed as part of the BDVe project with the collaboration of the BDVA. This initiative is based upon a committee of experts, from both academia and industry, which will define and maintain a list of skills required to play key roles in the data science ecosystem.

1 Introduction

Data scientists need, for example,

- widely recognized and verifiable credentials;

employers need, among others,

- tools to compare candidates, and
- a way to verify the authenticity of credentials;

while educators need, for example,

- feedback from industry regarding their programs, and
- the added value of an externally branded recognition.

To meet those needs, a scheme for the recognition of data science skills is being developed as part of the BDVe project¹. This recognition system involves the use of a hybrid approach, drawing upon aspects of traditional badge and certificate recognitions, in the form of Open Badges. Badges can be useful tools for recognizing learning and for motivating students [2]. Their use as alternatives to traditional credentials has also been discussed [1].

¹<https://www.big-data-value.eu/>

2 Badges for Data Science Skills

The EDSF of the EDISON project [3] with modifications based upon feedback from industry and academia, is being used as the basis of the required skills for the program. Five badges (Data Science Analytics, Data Engineering, Data Science Management, Business Process Management, and Data Science Research Methods) at two levels (academic and professional) are planned. As an example, the required skills for the Data Science Analytics Badge are currently as follows:

- DSA.1 Identify existing requirements to choose and execute the most appropriate data discovery techniques to solve a problem depending on the nature of the data and the goals to be achieved.
- DSA.2 Select the most appropriate techniques to understand and prepare data prior to modeling to deliver insights.
- DSA.3 Assess, adapt, and combine data sources to improve analytics.
- DSA.4 Use the most appropriate metrics to evaluate and validate results, proposing new metrics for new applications if required.
- DSA.5 Design and evaluate analysis tools to discover new relations in order to improve decision-making.
- DSA.6 Use visualization techniques to improve the presentation of the results of a data science project in any of its phases.

Experts from both industry and academia will periodically review the required skills for the badges and modify them to meet current needs. Programs which issue badges will thereby be encouraged to update their training. The work-flow of issuing badges at the academic level is as follows:

1. An educational program applies to issue a badge providing evidence regarding how the badge's skills are taught and evaluated;
2. Experts from industry and academia evaluate the application;
3. The program trains data science students and evaluates their skills;
4. Once students demonstrate that they meet the requirements of a badge, the program issues them a badge; and
5. Student display their badges online and in job applications.

A pilot of the academic level of the Data Science Analytics Badge will be run in the spring of 2019.

3 Credits

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This work was produced as part of the BDVe project, further information can be found on the BDVe web page:

<http://www.big-data-value.eu/skills/skills-recognition-program>.

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References

- [1] AHN, J., PELLICONE, A., AND BUTLER, B. Open badges for education: what are the implications at the intersection of open systems and badging? *Research in Learning Technology* 22 (Aug. 2014).
- [2] FACEY-SHAW, L., SPECHT, M., VAN ROSMALEN, P., BRNER, D., AND BARTLEY-BRYAN, J. Educational functions and design of badge systems: A conceptual literature review. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies* 11, 4 (Oct 2018), 536–544.
- [3] THE EDISON PROJECT. The EDISON data science framework. <https://github.com/EDISONcommunity/EDSF>.